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Fundamentals of Video Surveillance

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Automated Video Surveillance

Primary goal is situation awareness: fusing information from multiple sensors into a coherent model of actors, actions and events to help a remote user to understand what is happening (e.g. who is where; who is doing what to whom).

Motivation

Motivation

Example: Crowd Analysis

Automated video analysis of crowds in public spaces using computer vision tools

- Real-time monitoring
 - situation awareness
 - notification / alarms
- After-action review
 - trend analysis
 - analyze abnormal events

Measuring Crowd Flow/Density

Motivation

- Assisted Living
- “Smart Spaces”

Alzheimer's ward of
a nursing home

J.Gao, R.Collins, A.Hauptmann and H.Wactler,
"Articulated Motion Modeling for Activity Analysis,"
IEEE Workshop on Articulated and NonRigid Motion, in
conjunction with CVPR'04, Washington, DC, 2004.

Motivation

Overview

Part 1: Change/Motion Detection

Basics: BG subtraction; Frame Difference

Classification-based methods

Part 2: From Pixels to 2D Blobs

Detection via RJMCMC

Classifier Grids

Part 3: Data Association

Linear Assignment Problem

Murty K-best; PDAF; JPDAF

Part 4: Persistent Tracking

Adaptive Tracking

Tracking as Classification

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Part1 : Change Detection

Goal: Learn methods for pixel-level motion / change detection
Understand pros and cons of basic approaches

Basics of Video

Frames come in 30 times per second. This is not much time to process each image. Real-time algorithms therefore tend to be very simple.

One of the main features of video imagery is the temporal consistency from frame to frame. Not much changes during $1/30$ of a second!

Detecting Moving Objects

Assumption: objects that move are important (e.g. people and vehicles)

Basic approach: maintain a model of the static background. Compare the current frame with the background to locate moving foreground objects.

Simple Background Subtraction

- Background model is a static image (assumed to have no objects present).
- Pixels are labeled as object (1) or not object (0) based on thresholding the absolute intensity difference between current frame and background.


```
B = I(0);
```

```
...
```

```
loop time t
```

```
    I(t) = next frame;
```

```
    diff = abs[B - I(t)];
```

```
    M(t) = threshold(diff,  $\lambda$ );
```

```
...
```

```
end
```

Background Subtraction Results

**Simple Background
Subtraction**

movie

BG Observations

Background subtraction does a reasonable job of extracting the shape of an object, provided the object intensity/color is sufficiently different from the background.

BG Observations

Objects that enter the scene and stop continue to be detected, making it difficult to detect new objects that pass in front of them.

If part of the assumed static background starts moving, both the object and its negative ghost (the revealed background) are detected

BG Observations

Background subtraction is sensitive to changing illumination and unimportant movement of the background (for example, trees blowing in the wind, reflections of sunlight off of cars or water).

Background subtraction cannot handle movement of the camera.

Simple Frame Differencing

- Background model is replaced with the previous image.


```
B(0) = I(0);  
...  
loop time t  
    I(t) = next frame;  
    diff = abs[B(t-1) - I(t)];  
    M(t) = threshold(diff,  $\lambda$ );  
    ...  
    B(t) = I(t);  
end
```

Frame Differencing Results

**Simple Frame
Differencing**

movie

FD Observations

Frame differencing is very quick to adapt to changes in lighting or camera motion.

Objects that stop are no longer detected. Objects that start up do not leave behind ghosts.

However, frame differencing only detects the leading and trailing edge of a uniformly colored object. As a result very few pixels on the object are labeled, and it is very hard to detect an object moving towards or away from the camera.

Differencing and Temporal Scale

Note what happens when we adjust the temporal scale (frame rate) at which we perform two-frame differencing ...

$$\text{Define } D(N) = \| I(t) - I(t+N) \|^2$$

$I(t)$

$D(-1)$

$D(-3)$

$D(-5)$

$D(-9)$

$D(-15)$

more complete object silhouette, but two copies
(one where object used to be, one where it is now).

Three-Frame Differencing

The previous observation is the motivation behind three-frame differencing

Three-Frame Differencing

Choice of good frame-rate for three-frame differencing depends on the size and speed of the object

Adaptive Background Subtraction

- Current image is “blended” into the background model with parameter α
- $\alpha = 0$ yields simple background subtraction, $\alpha = 1$ yields frame differencing

Adaptive BG Subtraction Results

**Adaptive Background
Subtraction**

movie

Adaptive BG Observations

Adaptive background subtraction is more responsive to changes in illumination and camera motion.

Fast small moving objects are well segmented, but they leave behind short “trails” of pixels.

Objects that stop, and ghosts left behind by objects that start, gradually fade into the background.

The centers of large slow moving objects start to fade into the background too! This can be “fixed” by decreasing the blend parameter A , but then it takes longer for stopped/ghost objects to disappear.

Persistent Frame Differencing

- Motion images are combined with a linear decay term
- also known as motion history images (Davis and Bobick)


```

B(0) = I(0);
H(0) = 0;
loop time t
  I(t) = next frame;
  diff = abs[B(t-1) - I(t)];
  M(t) = threshold(diff, λ);
  tmp = max[H(t-1) - γ, 0];
  H(t) = max[255 * M(t), tmp];
  ...
  B(t) = I(t);
end

```

Persistent FD Results

**Persistent Frame
Differencing**

movie

Persistent FD Observations

Persistent frame differencing is also responsive to changes in illumination and camera motion, and stopped objects / ghosts also fade away.

Objects leave behind gradually fading trails of pixels. The gradient of this trail indicates the apparent direction of object motion in the image.

Although the centers of uniformly colored objects are still not detected, the leading and trailing edges are made wider by the linear decay, so that perceptually (to a person) it is easier to see the whole object.

Comparisons

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Comparisons

Interpreting Bg Subtraction

- What is a good statistical model of the value of a pixel in the unchanging background?

Interpreting Bg Subtraction

- What is a good statistical model of the value of a pixel in the unchanging background?

Interpreting Bg Subtraction

- Gaussian at each pixel. Adaptive mean (recursive estimator), constant variance.
- Detect outlier observations as foreground.

Interpreting Bg Subtraction

- Interpret change detection as two-class classification
- On the board: Work out the math of simple bg subtraction as classification.
- Basic ideas: background model is Gaussian with adaptive mean and constant variance. Foreground model is uniform distribution (or Gaussian with large variance).

Generative vs. Discriminative

Credit: C. Bishop, ICPR 2004

Generative vs. Discriminative Models

- **Generative approach:** separately model class-conditional densities and priors

$$p(\mathbf{x}|\mathcal{C}_k), \quad p(\mathcal{C}_k)$$

- then evaluate posterior probabilities using Bayes' theorem

$$p(\mathcal{C}_k|\mathbf{x}) = \frac{p(\mathbf{x}|\mathcal{C}_k)p(\mathcal{C}_k)}{\sum_j p(\mathbf{x}|\mathcal{C}_j)p(\mathcal{C}_j)}$$

- **Discriminative approach:** directly model posterior probabilities

$$p(\mathcal{C}_k|\mathbf{x})$$

Credit: C. Bishop, ICPR 2004

Interpreting Bg Subtraction

- Recursively estimating mean of Gaussian model of background appearance at each pixel (independently)
- Adaptive update of background values automatically takes care of slow appearance changes (e.g. lighting)

Limitation of Gaussian Assumption

- There is a problem with multimodal pixels
- Examples: trees in the wind; rippling water

Idea: Use a Mixture of Gaussians!

- Linear combination of Gaussians

$$p(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x} | \boldsymbol{\mu}_k, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_k)$$

- Normalization and positivity requirements

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k = 1 \quad 0 \leq \pi_k \leq 1$$

Statistical Background Modeling

Mixture of Gaussians in RGB space for background modeling.

Chris Stauffer and Eric Grimson, "Learning Patterns of Activity using Real-time Tracking," IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, Vol 22(8), August 2000, pp. 747-757.

Recent (improved) code available from Zivkovic.

<http://staff.science.uva.nl/~zivkovic/DOWNLOAD.html>

Statistical Background Modeling

Nonparametric statistical model using kernel density estimation (KDE)

Ahmed Elgammal, David Harwood, Larry Davis “Non-parametric Model for Background Subtraction”, 6th European Conference on Computer Vision. Dublin, Ireland, June 2000.

Sheikh and Shah

Model background **AND** foreground using kernel density estimator on 5-dimensional space of joint spatial-range data (x,y,r,g,b).

Example of Foreground Model

(a)

X-Y marginal

(b)

Pairwise color marginals

(c)

(d)

(e)

Sheikh and Shah

- Model background AND foreground appearance

$$P(\mathbf{x}|\psi_b) = n^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n \varphi_H(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}_i), \quad \text{KDE}$$

$$P(\mathbf{x}|\psi_f) = \alpha\gamma + (1 - \alpha)m^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^m \varphi_H(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z}_i) \quad \text{Uniform+KDE}$$

- Classification uses likelihood ratio

$$\tau = -\ln \frac{P(\mathbf{x}|\psi_b)}{P(\mathbf{x}|\psi_f)} = -\ln \frac{n^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n \varphi_H(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}_i)}{\alpha\gamma + (1 - \alpha)m^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^m \varphi_H(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z}_i)}.$$

Thus, the classifier δ is,

$$\delta(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{cases} -1 & \text{if } -\ln \frac{P(\mathbf{x}|\psi_b)}{P(\mathbf{x}|\psi_f)} > \kappa \\ 1 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

Other Feature Spaces

Some examples include:

Optic flow. Robert Pless, Spatio-temporal background models for outdoor surveillance. *Journal on Applied Signal Processing*, 14:2281–2291, 2005

Texture measures (local binary patterns). Heikkilä, M. and Pietikäinen, M. (2006), A Texture-Based Method for Modeling the Background and Detecting Moving Objects. *IEEE Trans. Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* 28(4):657-662.

Detector confidence scores. Stalder et.al. “Cascaded Confidence Filtering for Improved Tracking-by-Detection,” to appear, *ECCV 2010*.

Other Feature Spaces

Example: Detector Confidence Scores

From M Hebert at CMU

Stabilizing Camera Motion

Video in

Reference view

Warped video

Subtraction

Apparent motion of a panning/tilting camera can be removed by warping images into alignment with a collection of background reference views.

Tends not to work well for background subtraction. The background changes while you are not looking at it, causing a false positive detection when you do finally look.

Stabilization works better for frame differencing.

Frank Dellaert and Robert Collins,
“Fast Image-Based Tracking by
Selective Pixel Integration,” ICCV
Workshop on Frame-Rate Vision,
Corfu, Greece, Sept 1999.

Understanding Frame Differencing

Recall the brightness constancy equation for computing optic flow

$$\frac{\partial I}{\partial x} \frac{dx}{dt} + \frac{\partial I}{\partial y} \frac{dy}{dt} + \frac{\partial I}{\partial t} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial I}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial I}{\partial y} \quad (\text{spatial derivatives})$$

$$\frac{dx}{dt}, \frac{dy}{dt} = (\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) \quad (\text{optical flow; motion vector})$$

$$\frac{\partial I}{\partial t} \quad (\text{temporal derivative} = \text{frame difference!})$$

Understanding Frame Differencing

Recall the brightness constancy equation for computing optic flow

$$\frac{\partial I}{\partial x} \frac{dx}{dt} + \frac{\partial I}{\partial y} \frac{dy}{dt} + \frac{\partial I}{\partial t} = 0$$

Observations:

If there is no optical flow (motionless pixels), then frame difference should be zero (or very small due to random noise).

Conversely, if frame difference is large enough magnitude, then that implies motion at that pixel. [changing brightness breaks this implication]

If no spatial gradient at a pixel (uniform region) then frame difference will be zero even if there IS motion... so motion state is undefined in those areas.

If brightness constancy does not hold, frame differencing can fail.

Our Work in this Area

Basic Idea: Generalize persistent frame differencing to include both spatial and temporal smoothing, and to use temporal information from frames both forwards and backwards in time from the current frame.

- **Z.Yin and R.Collins, “Belief Propagation in a 3D Spatio-temporal MRF for Moving Object Detection, IEEE Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), 2007.**
- **Z.Yin and R.Collins, “Moving Object Localization in Thermal Imagery by Forward-Backwards MHI, IEEE Workshop on Object Tracking and Classification in and Beyond the Visible Spectrum (OTCBVS), 2006.**
- **Z.Yin and R.Collins, paper in preparation on Spatially Tuned Message Passing.**

MRF-based Motion Detection

consider a spatio-temporal
sequence of video frames

Filtering

compute motion based
on previous frames
(recursive)

Smoothing

compute motion based on
previous and future frames
(sliding window – fixed lag)

MRF-based Motion Detection

Consider grid where each pixel has is 6-connected
(4 spatial neighbors, 2 temporal neighbors)

MRF-based Motion Detection

These nodes will be our “hidden” states representing motion / no-motion.

Each hidden state is also connected to an observed state (in our case a pixel difference)

MRF-based Motion Detection

This setup has only pairwise cliques.

We define a simple compatibility function on each clique via the “Potts model” (each pixel encouraged to have same state value as its neighbors).

MRF-based Motion Detection

Consider temporal cliques, processing one pixel through time.
Note, this graphical model looks like a HMM. To compute optimal state value (or distribution over state values) at any node, we can do message passing.

MRF-based Motion Detection

Message passing for filtering (Forward only)

MRF-based Motion Detection

**Message passing for smoothing (fixed-lag smoothing).
Forward-Backward message passing.**

MRF-based Motion Detection

Specific instantiation.

Binary state: (no-motion , motion)

Each hidden node contains distribution $v = (a , 1-a)$.

Compatibility represented by Potts model $P = \begin{pmatrix} p & 1-p \\ 1-p & p \end{pmatrix}$

MRF-based Motion Detection

Messages specify what distribution each node thinks its neighbor should have.

MRF-based Motion Detection

Data messages:

If temporal difference magnitude at pixel is over threshold:

[0 , 1] confident of motion

otherwise

[.5 , .5] equally uncertain about motion / no motion

(alternatively could choose to use [1, 0])

MRF-based Motion Detection

Internal message passing:

compute “belief” at node from incoming messages

$$\text{bvector} = (M_{d2} .* M_{12}) / \text{dotprod}(M_{d2}, M_{12})$$

marginalize pairwise compatibility wrt belief

$$M_{12} = \text{bvector} * P$$

MRF-based Motion Detection

Example:

MRF-based Motion Detection

Forward only temporal filtering

**Showing MMSE at each pixel.
This is expected value of the
belief at each pixel.**

MRF-based Motion Detection

Forward only temporal filtering

Note: this looks a *lot* like motion history image (MHI) processing. In fact, you can show it *is* an MHI, with an exponential decay function.

MRF-based Motion Detection

Backward only temporal filtering

MHI in the opposite direction.

MRF-based Motion Detection

Forward/Backward

**Better delineation. No “trails”.
Reduced noise.**

MRF-based Motion Detection

So far we only looked at temporal cliques.
Must also consider spatial ones.

We use the same Potts model compatibility function
(each pixel encouraged to be in same state as neighbors).

MRF-based Motion Detection

Consider message passing on the spatial grid...

MRF-based Motion Detection

Consider message passing on the spatial grid...

**Problem, there are loops (cycles) in the graph.
Message passing is not strictly correct when used
on loopy graphs (may not even converge).**

MRF-based Motion Detection

Solution:

**Go ahead and use message passing anyways!
(also called loopy belief propagation)**

It often works very well in practice.

**There is a lot of work going on currently to
characterize when and why this works.**

Accelerated Message Passing

Current State of the Art

Yin and Collins: Add directional message passing based on considering the aperture problem (what components of “flow” are observable).

Qualitative evaluation

Red masks
from ours

Ours

Frame
differencing

OpenCV
adaptive bg

Dense
optical flow

Current State of the Art

Yin and Collins Results

Video demos

Current State of the Art

1. Motion segmentation

Video demo

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Current State of the Art

Yin and Collins results

Video demos

Next Step

Group foreground pixels into “blobs” that we can count or track.

Overview

Part 1: Change/Motion Detection

Basics: BG subtraction; Frame Difference

Classification-based methods

Part 2: From Pixels to 2D Blobs

Detection via RJMCMC

~~Classifier Grids~~

Part 3: Data Association

Linear Assignment Problem

Murty K-best; PDAF; JPDAF

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Adaptive Tracking

Tracking as Classification

The Story so Far...

We can classify foreground pixels based on background subtraction or frame differencing.

Next Task

Grouping pixels... into blobs

Can we use Connected Components?

Problem: Blob Merge/Split

When two objects pass close to each other, they are grouped as a single blob. Often, one object will become occluded by the other one. One of the challenging problems is to maintain correct labeling of each object after they split again.

Difficulty

Each of these gets harder as the crowd gets denser!

Main components of a video surveillance system:

- Background subtraction
- Connected components to get blobs
- Data association to get trajectories

Our Approach*

Bayesian Marked Point Process

- the prior models expected size/shape of people, indexed by location
- the likelihood measures how well a proposed configuration explains the data
- MAP estimate of number/configuration of people is found using RJ-MCMC

*Weina Ge and R.Collins, "Marked Point Processes for Crowd Counting,"
IEEE Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, Miami, FL, June 2009.

Foreground Object Detection

Bayesian Approaches

Non-Bayesian
[Dalal05; Rabaud06]

Pixel-wise MRF models
[Sheikh05]

Object-level models
(MPP)

Gibbs Point Process
[Ortner08]

Conditional Bayesian Models
[Rue99; Zhao03]

Marked Point Process

- Spatial Point Process
 - Distribution of a set of points in a bounded space
- Marked Point Process (MPP)
 - A spatial point process + a “mark” process
- Examples
 - Spatial process could model tree locations in a forest and the mark could be tree height
 - Spatial process could model cell locations on a microscope slide and the mark could be a polygonal representation of the cell boundary [Rue and Hurn, 1999]

Simplified Problem Statement

Given a foreground image, find a configuration of bounding boxes* that cover a majority of foreground pixels while leaving a majority of background pixels uncovered.

foreground
image

person-sized
bounding box

As an MPP:

- Spatial process models number and (x,y) locations of bounding boxes
- Mark process models (height,width,orientation) of each bounding box.

*Footnote: We will add more realistic “shape” models in a moment

Likelihood Score

To measure how “good” a proposed configuration is, we generate a foreground image from it and compare with the observed foreground image to get a likelihood score.

$$\text{config} = \{\{x_1, y_1, w_1, h_1, \text{theta}_1\}, \{x_2, y_2, w_2, h_2, \text{theta}_2\}, \{x_3, y_3, w_3, h_3, \text{theta}_3\}\}$$

Likelihood Score

Bernoulli distribution
model

- $p_{00} = p(y_i = 0|x_i = 0)$ = prob of observing background given a label of background
- $p_{01} = p(y_i = 0|x_i = 1)$ = prob of observing background given a label of foreground
- $p_{10} = p(y_i = 1|x_i = 0)$ = prob of observing foreground given a label of background
- $p_{11} = p(y_i = 1|x_i = 1)$ = prob of observing foreground given a label of foreground

- c_{00} = count of pixels where observation is background and label is background
- c_{01} = count of pixels where observation is background and label is foreground
- c_{10} = count of pixels where observation is foreground and label is background
- c_{11} = count of pixels where observation is foreground and label is foreground

likelihood

$$L(Y|X) = \prod_{i=1}^N p(y_i|x_i) = p_{00}^{c_{00}} p_{01}^{c_{01}} p_{10}^{c_{10}} p_{11}^{c_{11}}$$

simplify, by assuming

$$p_{00} = p_{11} = \mu \quad \text{and} \quad p_{01} = p_{10} = 1 - \mu$$

log likelihood

$$\begin{aligned} \log L(Y|X) &= (c_{00} + c_{11}) \log \mu + (c_{01} + c_{10}) \log(1 - \mu) \\ &= [N - (c_{01} + c_{10})] \log \mu + (c_{01} + c_{10}) \log(1 - \mu) \\ &= N \log \mu - (c_{01} + c_{10}) [\log \mu - \log(1 - \mu)] \end{aligned}$$

Number of pixels
that disagree!

Prior Model

We use a prior to model our expectations about bounding box configurations in the image

$$\pi(\mathbf{o}_i) = \pi(p_i) \pi(w_i, h_i, \theta_i | p_i)$$

Prior for
bounding
box i

Prior on location
(center point)

Prior on bounding box
height, width and orientation,
conditioned on center location.

Estimating Priors

Example: learning height distribution as a function of image row

Estimating Priors

Example: learning orientation as a function of image location

sample frame

extracted blobs / axes

SU-VLPR2010 extracted from training sequence

inliers for VP estimation

Estimating Priors

estimated vanishing point

Scaled, oriented rectangles

Bottom line: it is not difficult to estimate priors on location, size and orientation of people as seen from a specific viewpoint.

Searching for the Max

The space of configurations is very large. We can't exhaustively search for the max likelihood configuration. We can't even really uniformly sample the space to a reasonable degree of accuracy.

$$\text{config}_k = \{\{x_1, y_1, w_1, h_1, \text{theta}_1\}, \{x_2, y_2, w_2, h_2, \text{theta}_2\}, \dots, \{x_k, y_k, w_k, h_k, \text{theta}_k\}\}$$

Let N = number of possible locations for (x_i, y_i) in a k -person configuration.

Size of $\text{config}_k = N^k$

And we don't even know how many people there are...

Size of config space = $N^0 + N^1 + N^2 + N^3 + \dots$

If we also wanted to search for width, height and orientation, this space would be even more huge.

Searching for the Max

- Local Search Approach
 - Given a current configuration, propose a small change to it
 - Compare likelihood of proposed config with likelihood of the current config
 - Decide whether to accept the change

Proposals

- Add a rectangle (birth)

Proposals

- Remove a rectangle (death)

Proposals

- Move a rectangle

Searching for the Max

- Naïve Acceptance

- Accept proposed configuration if it has a larger likelihood score, i.e.

$$\text{Compute } a = \frac{L(\text{proposed})}{L(\text{current})}$$

Accept if $a > 1$

- Problem: leads to hill-climbing behavior that gets stuck in local maxima

Searching for the Max

- The MCMC approach
 - Generate random configurations from a distribution proportional to the likelihood!

Searching for the Max

- The MCMC approach
 - Generate random configurations from a distribution proportional to the likelihood!

- This searches the space of configurations in an efficient way.
- Now just remember the generated configuration with the highest likelihood.

MCMC in Action

Sequence of proposed configurations

Sequence of “best” configurations

movies

MCMC in Action

MAP configuration

Looking good!

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Examples

Example: Nov 22, Curtin Road

count 94

Example: Sep 6, Gate A

count 37

Adding Shape to the Estimation

Intrinsic vs Extrinsic Shape

Intrinsic shapes:
(silhouettes, aligned
and normalized)

Extrinsic shape
(how bounding box of
silhouette maps into
the image)

Revised Prior Model

$$\pi(\mathbf{o}_i) = \pi(p_i) \pi(w_i, h_i, \theta_i | p_i) \pi(s_i)$$

Prior for
object i

Prior on extrinsic shape
(location + bounding box
height, width and orientation)

Prior on intrinsic
shape selection

Learning Intrinsic Shapes

Silhouette shape represented as a Bernoulli mixture model

$$p(\mathbf{x}|\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\pi}) = \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k p(x|\boldsymbol{\mu}_k)$$

Training shapes
(foreground masks)

Learned Bernoulli
mixture model
("soft" silhouettes)

Learning Intrinsic Shapes

“standard” EM

Bayesian EM with Dirichlet prior

Provides automatic selection of number of mixture components

Adding Shape to the Estimation

MCMC iterations

movie

MCMC proposes changes to current configuration

- add/remove a person
- shift location of person
- change their shape**

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VSPETS Soccer Dataset

Evaluation run on every 10th frame
green contours: true positives
red boxes: false negatives
pink contours: false positives

movie

detailed view

SI

count=4

count=4

count=4

count=4

count=3

count=4

count=4